

Proactive Personality and Internal Locus of Control as Predictors of Job Satisfaction Among Secondary School Teachers in Onitsha Metropolis

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine the prediction among proactive personality, internal locus of control and job satisfaction among secondary school teachers in Onitsha metropolis. The study adopted the correlation survey research design. The sample for the study comprised 163 secondary school teachers in Onitsha metropolis. The instruments for data collection were the proactive personality scale, internal locus of control scale and Job satisfaction instrument. Data collected were analysed using multiple regression analysis. The findings of the study revealed that proactive personality of the secondary school teachers contributed to 51.0 percent for their job satisfaction. Therefore, secondary school teachers' proactive personality is a significant predictor of their job satisfaction. The findings further revealed that that internal locus of control of the secondary school teachers contributed to -8.2 percent for their job satisfaction. Therefore, secondary school teachers' internal locus of control is not a significant predictor of their job satisfaction. This indicates that proactive behaviour, internal locus of control of teachers jointly have contributed to 74.6 percent for their job satisfaction. Therefore, secondary school teachers' proactive personality and locus of control jointly are significant predictors of their job satisfaction. It was concluded that secondary school teachers' in Onitsha Metropolis proactive personality and locus of control jointly are significant predictors of their jobsatisfaction. On the other hand, the study has implications on teachers, school administrators, counsellors among others.

Key words: Proactive, personality, locus of control, job satisfaction, secondary school, teachers

Introduction

Researchers have always developed interest in distilling the components of job satisfaction and understanding what factors contribute to its increase among employees at work. Given the centrality of the job satisfaction construct in industrial/organizational psychology, job satisfaction has been correlated with several important organizational outcome variables. Satisfaction is an intrapsychic state of pleasure, happiness or achievement. It is indeed a non-detachable part of the human well-being. Most of all human activities are geared towards attaining this state of contentedness and blissfulness. Satisfaction keeps us aligned to appropriateness in our different engagements towards our long and short-term goals. While some

people see work as an essential activity merely geared toward earning a living, others go deep in accepting work as to that which should bring happiness and satisfaction. Job satisfaction is of a paramount desire to all workers. The importance of Satisfaction with job cannot be underrated in the assessment of the wellbeing of individuals and their organizations. Job satisfaction is an individual's subjective viewpoint encompassing the way they feel about their job and the employing organization, job satisfaction is the pleasurable emotional state that results from the achievement of job values (Cronley & Kim, 2017). Satisfaction is influenced by a broad range of concepts and variables of which personality and environmental factors are strong holds. In this light, this study examines the relationship between proactive personality on job satisfaction. This study also examines the relationship between perceived organizational support as it relates to job satisfaction. And it finally studies the mediating role of self-efficacy between proactive personality, psychological contract on job satisfaction.

Job satisfaction refers to how pleased a worker or an employee is with their current job. It is a state of mind that a worker or employee holds with regards to how comfortable they are with the very job they are doing. Job satisfaction is "the extent to which one is happy with one's job; hence an employee's willingness to perform to an optimum level (Hoffman- Miller, 2013). Job satisfaction is a worker's sense of achievement and success on the job. It is generally perceived to be directly linked to personal well-being. It implies one doing a job one enjoys doing well and being rewarded for one's efforts. Job satisfaction further implies "enthusiasm and happiness with one's work (Kaliski, 2017). Job satisfaction is a feeling that can produce a positive or negative effect towards one's roles and responsibilities at work. Cranny, Smith and Stone (2014) defined job satisfaction as "employees' emotional state regarding the job considering what they expected and what they actually got. Job satisfaction is an overall assessment of "an individual's beliefs, affect, and evaluation of their job which could be positive or negative about his or her job or situation.

One's satisfaction with job could be greatly related to how one believes in one's own thoughts and abilities of making things happen, this could be loosely translated to "I can do it" belief. Self-efficacy is the belief people have in their own abilities especially in their abilities to meet challenges ahead of them and complete a task successfully (Akhtar 2018). General self-efficacy refers to our overall belief in our capability to make it or succeed in our endeavours. According to Bandura (1997) it is the belief that one can perform novel or difficult tasks, or cope with adversity in various domains of human functioning. Self-efficacy also narrows down to the belief in one's own effectiveness in performing specific tasks, it also furthers into one's sense of control. This level of one's sense of control determines the level at which one will engage in productive behaviours. It could go as far as mediating all other factors that influence job satisfaction since it center on self-influenced ability of succeeding no matter how the situation might be.

Personality factor such as proactive personality is not left out to ascertain job satisfaction. Proactive personality is an inherent disposition which enables an individual to take actions that are positive in influencing his or her environment. Proactivity refers to active attempts made by an individual to effect changes to his or her environment (Zampetakis in Bernard, Osinachi and Ogbonnia, 2019). Bernard, Osinachi and Ogbonnia, (2019) described proactivity as taking initiative in improving and challenging the status quo rather than passively adapting to present conditions. Personality factor as proactive personality is liable to influence an employee's love for his or her job and a sense of achievement in life. This dispositional factor of someone's natural trait and genetics is based on the tendency that one's satisfaction is partly derived from each persons' disposition can leave a significant effect on their job attitudes, this in turn can reflect positively or negatively on satisfaction. Researchers estimate that "30% of an employee's job satisfaction is associated with dispositional factors.

Proactive work behaviours have more often been in focus. However, findings on the link between personality and proactive work behaviours are inconsistent at first view. Whereas Crant, Kim, and Wang (2011) found voice behaviour to be unrelated to all five personality factors, other studies reported a positive link between voice and conscientiousness, openness to experience, and extraversion (Tornau and Frese, 2013), and a negative relationship with neuroticism and agreeableness. An explanation for these differences might be the study design. Whereas Crant and colleagues (2011) conducted a field study and collected their data on voice behaviour in a three-hour experimental task. Such a controlled and time-constrained experimental setting might have promoted neurotic and agreeable tendencies and prevented voice behaviour (Crant et al., 2011). Similar inconsistencies occur for taking charge. A meta-analysis conducted by Tornau and Frese (2013) revealed that taking charge is positively affected by high values of conscientiousness, openness to experience, and extraversion, and negatively affected by neuroticism.

Agreeableness was unrelated to taking charge. Different findings are reported by Parker and Collins (2010) who did not find a significant link between conscientiousness and taking charge. This discrepancy might be due to the analyses. Parker and Collins (2010) regressed taking charge on conscientiousness and learning and performance goal orientation in one single regression step. Learning goal orientation was positively linked to taking charge, whereas performance goal orientation negatively affected taking charge. Individuals staying with a task and striving for a specific learning goal are more conscientious than employees showing a low learning goal orientation. Hence, individual variance in conscientiousness might have been explained by personal goal orientation. Further proactive work behaviours that have been investigated as outcomes of certain personality factors include problem prevention and individual innovation. Both were found to be unrelated to conscientiousness (Parker and Collins, 2010).

Similarly, another psychological factor that could hinder job satisfaction among teachers is locus of control. Locus of control derived from Rotter's social learning theory and from the individual interpretation made on their control level over events of life (Serin, 2010). Locus of control is referred to as the extent to which individuals believe that they can control events and causes of their actions. Locus of control is concerned with the question of whether or not an individual believes that his own behaviour, skills or internal disposition determine what reinforcements he receives and refers to a person's beliefs about control over life events (Martins, 2014). Teachers with internal locus of control believe that the consequences of their behaviour are under their personal control and that they are effective in controlling their destiny and determining the occurrence of reinforcement, and feel personally responsible for the things that happen to them. While those with external locus of control believe that the outcomes of their performances in life are determined by forces beyond their control (fate, chance, luck, powerful others and supernatural forces) and that they determine the occurrence of specified events. With respect to the nature and extent of the established relationships, it was found out that internal locus of control was negatively associated with job performance while external locus of control was positively associated with job satisfaction (Mustapha, 2016). However, the unsatisfactory state of affairs in job satisfaction among teachers in Onitsha Metropolis remains a source of concern to researchers. This propels the present study to determine proactive personality and internal locus of control as predictors of job satisfaction among secondary school teachers in Onitsha metropolis.

Research questions

1. Does proactive personality predict job satisfaction among secondary school teachers in Onitsha metropolis?
2. Does internal locus of control predict job satisfaction among secondary school teachers in Onitsha metropolis?

3. Does proactive personality, internal locus of control jointly predict job satisfaction among secondary school teachers in Onitsha metropolis?

Null Hypothesis

1. Secondary school teacher's proactive personality does not significantly predict their job satisfaction in Onitsha metropolis
2. Secondary school teacher's internal locus of control does not significantly predict their job satisfaction in Onitsha metropolis
3. Secondary school students' proactive personality and internal locus of control do not jointly predict job satisfaction in Onitsha metropolis?

Method

The study adopted the correlation survey research design. The sample for the study was drawn using the simple random sampling of balloting without replacement to select 163 teachers from secondary schools in Onitsha metropolis. The instruments for data collection were the proactive personality scale, internal locus of control scale and the Job satisfaction scale. The researchers and research assistants administered the instruments through direct delivery method. The researchers with the help of 11 well-trained research assistants, distributed the questionnaire to the respondents. The researchers had a briefing meeting with the research assistants during which they intimated them on the purpose of the research, contents of the questionnaires, how to administer the instrument and also how to collect them back. The researchers and assistants collected the completed copies of the questionnaires. For data analyses, research questions were answered using simple regression analysis. The null hypotheses were tested using simple and multiple regression analysis. For the hypotheses: where r calculated $>$ than r -critical, reject null hypothesis and where r -calculated $<$ than r -critical do not reject the null hypothesis. Also, where significant value of (P) is less than 0.05, reject null hypothesis, however, when the value (P) is greater than 0.05, do not reject the null hypothesis.

Results

Research question and hypothesis 1

Table 1: Regression analysis on the teachers' proactive personality as predictors of their job satisfaction

Sources of variation	R	R ²	R ² change	B	BET A	% variance added	Cal. F	Cal. t	df	Pvalue	Remark
Components	0.856	0.732	0.730			73.0	308.99			0.000	S
Internal locus of control				-1.065	-.072			2.48	161	0.014	S
Proactive personality				.346	.510			9.65		0.000	S

In table 1, it was observed that proactive personality of the secondary school teachers had Beta of 0.510. This indicates that proactive personality of the teachers had contributed to 51.0 percent for their job

satisfaction. Also, at 161df and 0.05 level of significant, the calculated t 9.65 with P value 0.000 which is less than the 0.05, the first null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, secondary school teachers' proactive personality is a significant predictor of their job satisfaction.

Research question and hypothesis 2

Table 2: Table 1: Regression analysis on the teachers' internal locus of control as predictors of their job satisfaction

Sources of variation	R	R ²	R ² change	B	BETA	% variance added	Cal. F	Cal. t	df	Pvalue	Remark
Components	0.852	0.725	0.717			71.7	84.54			0.000	S
Proactive personality				-1.446	-0.082			1.41	161	0.161	NS
Internal Locus of control				.177	.241			1.84		0.070	NS

Table 2 indicates that internal locus of control of the secondary school teachers had Beta of -0.082. This indicates that internal locus of control of teachers had contributed to -8.2 percent for their job satisfaction. Also, at 161df and 0.05 level of significant, the calculated t 1.41 with Pvalue 0.161 which is greater than the 0.05, the fourth null hypothesis is not rejected. Therefore, secondary school teachers' internal locus of control is not a significant predictor of their job satisfaction.

Research question and hypothesis 3

In conclusion, Table 1, shows that proactive behaviour and internal locus of control of the secondary school teachers jointly have R² adjusted of 0.746. This indicates that proactive behaviour, internal locus of control of teachers jointly have contributed to 74.6 percent for their job satisfaction.

Similarly, at 161df and 0.05 level of significant, the calculated F237.97 with Pvalue 0.000 which is less than the 0.05, the third null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, secondary school teachers' proactive personality and locus of control jointly are significant predictors of their job satisfaction.

Discussion

From the study, it was observed that secondary school teachers' proactive personality had predictor variable that accounted for 51 percent of variance in teachers' job satisfaction. This indicated that internal locus of control of teachers had contributed 51 percent for job satisfaction. This therefore shows that internal locus of control of secondary school teachers Onitsha metropolis is a significant predictor of their job satisfaction. This finding affirms to Bernard, Osinachi and Ogbonnia, (2019) who found that individual who are proactive in nature are more likely to be satisfied at work and are dominating, self-confident and achieve much.

The result of this study revealed that internal locus of control of the secondary school teachers had Beta of -0.082. This indicates that internal locus of control of teachers had contributed to -8.2 percent for their job

satisfaction. This internal locus of control is a predictor of job satisfaction among workers. Also, Dollinger (2016) reported that internal locus of control is a predictor of job satisfaction. Spector(2008) observation is in line with the findings that individuals with internal locus of control are more job satisfied because they are less likely to be more committed to the task and are more likely to be successful in the organization. The reason for this could be attributed to the fact that counsellors' with an internal locus of control developed ways to shield stress, regardless of job challenges and are more satisfied with their jobs while those counsellors' with an external locus of control relied on chance and external support to reduce job dissatisfaction.

In this study, the analyses showed that secondary school teachers in Onitsha metropolis proactive personality and locus of control have jointly predictors' variable that accounted for 73 percent of variance in teachers job satisfaction. This indicates proactive personality and locus of control of counsellor had contributed 73 percent for the job satisfaction. This therefore shows that Secondary school teachers' marital status and internal locus of control jointly are significant predictors of their job satisfaction in Onitsha metropolis.

The study agrees with the view of Waite and Gallagher (2010) that predictive variety of positive effect on job satisfaction of the individual and families. The finding is in agreement with Oesterman (2013) that external locus of control is not a predictor of job satisfaction. Also Judges and Bono (2011) supported the claim of the study that there is a positive prediction between locus of control and job satisfaction. However, Stella and Peter affirm the finding of the study that counsellors with internal locus of control are more satisfied with their job and are successful in coping with difficulties inherent in the job. Based on this situation, one may further deduce that counsellors' with internal locus of control are more determined to change unpleasant events that may led to job dissatisfaction because they believed they determined the happening in their job while those counsellors' with external locus of control experiencing job dissatisfaction tend to attribute external forces such as luck or poor salary as the reason for their job dissatisfaction.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that secondary school teachers' in Onitsha Metropolis proactive personality and locus of control jointly are significant predictors of their job satisfaction. On the other hand, the study has implications on teachers, school administrators, counsellors among others. The study recommends that since proactive personality and internal locus of control are jointly predictors of job satisfaction among secondary school counsellors. Earnest efforts should be made by governments and counselling psychologists to enhance locus of control of counsellors for the purpose of transforming education in Nigeria. Counsellors with internal locus of control are more likely to create and promote conditions and interpersonal networks that nourish and sustain work satisfaction.

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